

(I)

	R	R ₁	R ₂
(a)	OH	H	H
(b)	H	OH	H
(c)	H	H	OH

The m.p.s of I (a), (b) and (c) were respectively 138° (d.), 130° (d.) & 141° (d.). The elemental analysis & molecular weight determination of these biflavonoids were in agreement with the molecular formula C₃₀H₂₆O₈.

The absence of ketonic peak in the IR spectra indicated that the flavanones have been completely reduced. On complete methylation with diazomethane I (a) gave a product which analysed for four methoxyl groups (found OCH₃, 21.3%; calc. for C₃₀H₂₂O₄ (OCH₃)₄, 21.7%). The methyl ether of the biflavonoid I (a) still showed the absorption for hydroxyl group (ν_{max} 3,350 and 3,450 cm⁻¹) in the IR-spectrum, thereby indicating the presence of hydroxyl groups. The methyl ether of I (a) on acetylation gave a diacetate which analysed for two acetyl groups, confirming the presence of two hydroxyl groups. Similar results were obtained for the methyl ethers of I (b) and I (c) and these analysed for four methoxyl groups and formed diacetates.

The methyl ether of I (a) on treatment with sodium metaperiodate consumed one mole of periodate per mole of the compound. Thus the presence of a *cis*-biflavandiol linked at I-4, II-4 positions in I (a) has been established.

The reduction products I (a), (b) and (c) when methylated with dimethyl sulphate yielded the corresponding tetramethyl ethers but prolonged treatment (20 hr.) under these experimental conditions gave the cyclic carbonates, which were found to be identical with the product obtained from the reaction of these dimeric methyl ethers with ethylchloroformate and alkali.

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Alkaloids from *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Roxb

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THE plant *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* (family *Elaeocarpaceae*) is commonly known as Rudraksha in India.

In the indigenous system of medicine the fruit is used in the treatment of epilepsy¹ and the seed is used in cardiac trouble². Earlier we reported³ some important pharmacological properties of the extracts of the seeds, e.g. pressure effect of long duration and marked positive inotropic effect on both intact and isolated mammalian hearts. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterization of two alkaloids from the leaves of the same plant.

From the ethanolic extract of the leaves of *E. ganitrus* two alkaloids have been isolated by preparative TLC over silica gel (Solvent system: benzene: chloroform: methanol=30:15:2, v/v).

The first alkaloid, C₁₆H₁₉NO₂, m. p., 81-82°, UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 320 nm. (ϵ 3200) and 253 nm (ϵ 8800), was characterized as (\pm) elaeocarpine by direct comparison (m. p., mixed m. p., TLC and GLC) with an authentic sample of (\pm) elaeocarpine⁴.

The second alkaloid, C₁₆H₁₉NO₂, m. p., 51-52°, UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 326 nm. (ϵ 3100) and 258 nm. (ϵ 9500), was characterized as (\pm) isoelaecarpine by direct comparison (m. p., mixed m. p., TLC and GLC) with an authentic sample of (\pm) isoelaecarpine⁴.

It may be mentioned here that (\pm) elaeocarpine and (\pm) isoelaecarpine are epimers. Their retention times (4.5 and 4.3 min. respectively) have been found to be different in GLC carried out under our experimental conditions (column 2%, S. E-33 nonpolar phase supported on 60-80 mesh gas chrom. Q and packed into a 6' x $\frac{1}{4}$ " stainless steel tube. The temperatures

used: oven 220°; I. P.-260°; F. I. D.-270°. Carrier gas nitrogen, 25 ml/min. The GLC apparatus used was an F & M, model 700 of Hewlett and Packard, (U. S. A.)

Due to the paucity of the plant material further investigation could not be undertaken.

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Determination of Ascorbic acid with Potassium iodate, Iodine, Potassium bromate and Iodine monochloride using Naphthol blue black, Amaranth and Brilliant Ponceau 5R as indicators

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ERDEY and Bodor⁷ standardised the ascorbic acid against potassium iodate or iodine solutions to the disappearance of the colour caused by iodine. Lorenz, Reynolds and Stevans² used starch as indicator in the titration of iodine. Ballantine³ used starch as indicator in the titration of potassium iodate. Szekers, Sugar and Pop⁴ used starch in the estimation of potassium bromate in the presence of potassium iodide. Cihalik⁵ used starch as indicator in the titration of ascorbic acid with iodine monochloride. But Erdey and Bodor⁷ and Gopala Rao and Narayana Rao⁶ were of the opinion that starch cannot be used as indicator in these titrations since it decreases the reaction rate between ascorbic acid and iodine. Variamine blue is proposed as the indicator in the place of starch by Eardey and Kaplar^{7a} and by Cihalik⁵ in the titrations of ascorbic acid with iodine and potassium iodate and in iodine monochloride respectively. Deshmukh and Bapat³ used carbon tetrachloride in the titration of potassium iodate. Singh, Kashyap and Sahota⁹ used chloroform in the presence of mercuric chloride in the

titration of ascorbic acid with iodine monochloride. Schulek, Kovaes and Rozsa¹⁰ used *p*-ethoxy chrysoidine as indicator with potassium bromate in the presence of potassium bromide. The authors stated that the end point is not so sharp as that of starch-iodide blue colour. In view of these varied concepts regarding the successful use of indicators we tried to use naphthol blue black, amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R in the standardisation and estimation of ascorbic acid with potassium iodate or iodine solutions. The indicators were also successfully used in the titrations of ascorbic acid with potassium bromate and iodine monochloride solutions.

Experimental

All the reagents used unless otherwise stated were of Analar (B. D. H.) quality. The indicators employed were of 0.2 per cent. aqueous solutions. 0.1*N* iodine¹¹ and iodine monochloride^{1a} solutions were prepared and standardised^{11,1a} against standard solution of arsenic(III) 0.1*N* potassium iodate and potassium bromate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals G.R. Proanalysis grade) were prepared and standardised iodometrically with sodium thiosulphate which in turn standardised with potassium dichromate.

0.1*N* solution of ascorbic acid (Sarabhai M. Chemicals G. R. Proanalysis grade) was prepared by dissolving required amount in one litre in the presence of stabilising agents EDTA and formic acid¹ and standardised against standard solution of potassium iodate¹.

Procedure: An aliquot volume of ascorbic acid is taken in a 150 ml. flask and the required amount of hydrochloric acid is added to give an over all acid concentration of 0.1-2.0*N* for potassium iodate, 0.1-1.0*N* for iodine, 0.2-0.3*N* for potassium bromate and 1-2.5*N* for iodine monochloride titrations. To the mixture about 0.1 ml. of the indicator solution is added and the titration is carried out against the respective oxidant. In the estimation of ascorbic acid with potassium iodate and potassium bromate 2-10 ml. of one per cent. solution of potassium iodide is added before the titration is carried. The colour changes are from blue to green for naphthol blue black and from rose pink to brownish yellow for both amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R. The colour changes are fairly reversible and the indicator correction is negligible in such titrations.

Reverse titration: Naphthol blue black, amaranth and brilliant ponceau 5R can as well be used as indicators in the titrations of potassium iodate, potassium bromate, iodine and iodine monochloride solutions with ascorbic acid. In the titrations of potassium iodate and potassium bromate 10 per cent. solution of potassium iodide is used to liberate the iodine correspondingly and the liberated iodine is titrated with ascorbic acid.

Chloride, sulphate, nitrate, acetate, borate, tartarate, citrate, phosphate, antimonate, potash alum, manganese(II), zinc(II), barium(II), glucose, sucrose, fructose,